

The Generations & Gender Programme

GGG-II Data Processing Manual

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Authors: Olga Grunwald & Aisling Connolly

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1 Background

Before the new round of data collection (GGS-II) began, we revised our data collection methods to address the challenges and shortcomings encountered during GGS-I. A pivotal revision was the implementation of a more centralized framework. The GGP team and the country teams now collaborate throughout the entire data life cycle. This entails close cooperation during the planning and preparation of fieldwork, active monitoring during fieldwork, and continued partnership during the data processing and documentation phases.

The close contact with country teams throughout the whole data life cycle gives us greater control during the process. We can monitor and advise the activities of participating countries and intervene when necessary to ensure alignment with standardised practices and enhance the comparability of their data with that of other countries.

To streamline the data collection process, we have introduced a core baseline questionnaire implemented across all countries, centrally coded using the Blaise software. While adhering to this core questionnaire, national teams retain the flexibility to tailor it to their specific contexts by incorporating additional questions or country-specific response options. This harmonization of questionnaire frameworks, coupled with close collaboration, has significantly bolstered compliance and coherence across fieldwork designs. Since we collaborate closely with national teams, the result is greater compliance with the questionnaire and fieldwork design. And, centralising coordination has enabled systematic documentation of country-specific variations during fieldwork and has advanced the data processing phase, rendering it more efficient.

When revising the data processing workflow, we had three primary objectives: to establish a straightforward and efficient workflow, to ensure uniformity the format of datasets across countries for seamless cross-national research, and to accelerate data release. Notably, the latter goal posed a considerable challenge due to the lengthy duration of fieldwork during which the baseline questionnaire has developed to correct for issues that were detected in earlier versions of the core. Nevertheless, we addressed this challenge by preparing a major update of all countries to correct for these issues and to harmonise the data from all countries so that cross-country comparison is as straightforward as possible.

In pursuit of these objectives, we developed an Empty Data File (EDF) serving as the template dataset for harmonisation across all countries. The data processing workflow is centred around the EDF, which contains all variable definitions, labels, response options, and question text but no actual data. The EDF is based on the coded version of the core questionnaire otherwise known as the CORE which holds all the relevant information. Each country also has a country CORE which is the coded version of the core questionnaire with the country-specific deviations included. To get from the CORE to the EDF, we have an R-script to extract the necessary information from the questionnaire code into an excel sheet. Then, we import the excel sheet into Stata which is formatted in such a way that Stata can automatically write it in do-files and generate the EDF. Automation of this process ensures with every modification of the CORE questionnaire, we can easily produce a new version of the EDF without having to make manual adjustments to it.

When we start processing the data for a new country, raw country data is imported into the EDF. This approach ensures that variables conform to standardized structures, simplifying data merging across countries for end-users. Any deviations specific to countries are already marked as country-specific in the country core and will therefore not be merged with the EDF.

Following data merging, additional steps are undertaken to finalize the processed data. This manual outlines the specific steps and explains their necessity to ensure transparency and reproducibility in GGS data processing practices. This documentation is instrumental not only in providing end-users with insights into the data processing workflow but also in facilitating internal collaboration within the GGP team and enhancing cooperation with external partners like INED.

2 Data cleaning steps

In data cleaning, the goal is to refine the dataset without altering its substance, ensuring that the 'cleaned' version retains all the essential information while modifying only its structure.

As the CORE or Blax (name of file types produced by Blaise) evolves and country-specific adaptations are made, the data cleaning code also needs to be adjusted accordingly. The do-files are organized in such a way that going forward, we will start from the same do-file in every country and adjust it as needed. There is one master do-file and several sub-do-files that have specific pieces of code that should run for every country.

The do-files are stored separately to make sure we always use the same ones. It is important to only make changes to the master do-file and not the sub-do-files as it will make it easier to understand where specific changes had to be made (as an alternative to adding comments). In instances where the standard sub-do-file do not work, the code can be copied into the master do-file and adjusted accordingly.

By enabling the selective activation of do-files in the master do-file, we enhance accessibility and convenience.

2.1 PART 1: Set standard settings

To ensure efficient collaboration between team members, it's crucial to establish standardised procedures for constructing and managing do-files and data processing setups. We implement this by using 'globals' to define data locations and file names, reducing the need for repetitive edits throughout the code. This approach allows us to make adjustments centrally at the outset, facilitating easier management and sharing of do-files among team members. Since each team member's folder path varies, all team members must specify their individual path. You can identify your username by executing the command `\display "c(username) ""`. This only need to be changed once at the start of the do-file.

Furthermore, for each new country, the country name, its identifying code (retrievable from the CORE), and the wave is included in the do-file. Global file pathways are then adjusted to align with users' folder paths for storing files and accessing raw data, as well as do-files for data cleaning. Additionally, country-specific ISO (country) and ISCO (occupation) codes provided by the national team are incorporated into the setup.

2.2 PART 2: Adjust raw data

The raw data is stored in a .txt format on Surfdrive. Although there is a .dta version of the data, we should avoid using it as the fieldwork team has already modified the data. By using the .txt version of the data, we start from the very raw version of the data.

The do-file "2_AdjustRawData" is responsible for preparing the data to be merged with the EDF (Empty Data File). It will remove the prefix of all variable labels that are added when exporting the data from Blaise. Potentially, there are additional prefixes to the variables depending on the country

so this should be checked with the Blax file. Additionally, all variable names from the data will be removed. Furthermore, variables that have been generated in Blaise will be dropped. These variables include date imputed and derived variables and routing variables such as whether the respondent has a child or a partner and if the respondent is a home owner. In the case of NO and MLD, these variables were initially released but later decided not to be included anymore due to potential confusion for users and difficulty in understanding them. Some of these variables were generated in a simplistic way, and their reconstruction using the variables in the data might not be accurate. Instead, they will be reconstructed and added to new data releases.

In certain countries, there was an error with the filtering regarding the respondents' child's age. We need to correct the variables that were mistakenly asked to respondents whose child was too young to receive those questions. This is necessary when the variable "childage" has values like 2021, 2022, etc. Therefore, these values are replaced with .y as a special missing answer category which is performed in the "2_AdjustRawData-CorrectFilter" do-file.

Questions on the time duration for respondents (Ttimedur) are asked as a string in the format "HHMM" which is then transformed into minutes to facilitate the use of variables. However, earlier countries used different formats, which required different data processing codes to transform the variables. A summary of which country used which "Ttimedur" format is listed below.

Country	Time duration format
Argentina	HH:MM
Austria	HH:MM
Croatia	HHMM
Czechia	HH:MM
Estonia	HHMM (error in lhi40_1-lhi40_20, contains non-numeric characters)
Finland	HHMM
Hong Kong	HH:MM
Moldova	HH:MM
Netherlands	MMMM
Norway	HH:MM
Uruguay	HHMM

The data may also include test IDs that need to be removed. The fieldwork team has modified the way they indicate a "respid" (respondent ID) is used for testing. Sometimes, there is a "test" included or a "T." These cases must be removed. In situations where it's unclear whether it is a test ID, the fieldwork team has a list of valid IDs. In earlier countries, the fieldwork team did not assign special "respid" for test IDs but shared a list with the data processing team.

If a country conducted the GGS in two languages, there could be instances where respondents logged in twice with different languages, resulting in duplicate IDs in the data. There could also be other reasons for double IDs. To ensure data accuracy, it is crucial to verify that the "respid" is unique.

Finally, the last step involves appending the raw data to the EDF. For this process to be successful, the variable names and formats of variables in the raw data must be identical to those in the EDF. Otherwise, the variables will not match and will appear at the bottom of the dataset. It's important to check the bottom of the variable list for any variables without labels, as these indicate that they have not been merged with the EDF. However, country-specific variables which include the country code in their name will not have labels.

2.3 PART 3: Merge codes

The GGS questionnaire contains several questions in which respondents have to select an answer from a list of countries (e.g. country of birth of respondent/partner/parents.) or occupations (e.g. respondent occupation, respondent's last occupation partner's occupation, parents occupation.). Respondents can choose from a range of different options by typing the first letters of a country / occupation and selecting the right answer. Countries are connected to an ISO Code and occupations to an ISCO Code: For example, Germany has the numeric **ISO Code 0276** and the occupation Baker has the numeric **ISCO Code 7512**. These codes make the answers comparable across countries.

ISO and ISCO code lists are provided by the country team which are linked in Blaise. Therefore, respondents see the string representation of the occupation/ country instead of the corresponding numeric code. However, sometimes the linking between the number and string fails in Blaise, resulting in a scenario where the string variable (without suffix) contains a value, but the corresponding numeric variable is missing. In early countries, there were instances where incorrect numbers were merged with the string. To address this issue, we re-establish the link between the code and the string.

The linking of codes and strings is based on the name of the occupation/country. The process involves creating a dataset containing the string and code, which is then merged with the main dataset using the string as the key. Consequently, the code from the main dataset is overwritten with the code from the list. This process is performed separately for countries and occupations with the "3_LinkingCodes_ISO/ISCO" do-files. The variables should be checked to ensure all codes have a corresponding string name and should be labelled accordingly if not.

The country and occupation lists are provided by the national team. However, errors can occur, especially in the occupation list, where an occupation may be mistakenly assigned two different ISCO codes. To ensure data accuracy, it is essential to check beforehand that the codes are unique. This verification can be conducted using the "3_LinkingCodes-UnitTest" do-file.

Another issue that may arise is the truncation of the string length in the data (str25), causing a mismatch with the corresponding strings in the list. This situation is less problematic for the country list as countries are usually identifiable by the first 25 characters. However, it poses a challenge for occupations, where the first 25 characters may be identical, but the subsequent characters differ and have different numeric codes. To resolve this, the names in the list also need to be shortened to ensure a match. Therefore, there are two different do-files to merge the ISCO codes, one with recasting ("3_LinkingCodes_ISCO-recast") and one without ("3_LinkingCodes_ISCO").

2.4 PART 4: Split date variable

The date variables are stored in one variable that contains both the month and the year. There are different ways in which the date questions have been asked and hence, the code differs and also the quality of the data differs which can be checked with the "4_Date-CheckFormat" do-file.

Country	Date format
Argentina	MMYYYY
Austria	MMYYYY
Croatia	MMYYYY
Czechia	MM/YYYY

Estonia	MMYYYY
Finland	MMYYYY
Hong Kong	MMYYYY
Moldova	MM/YYYY
Netherlands	MMYYYY
Norway	MM/YYYY
Uruguay	MMYYYY

For analyses, it is easier to have month and year as separate variables. Therefore, we split the original variable into a 'month' and a 'year' variable in the "4_Date" do-file.

A problem is that some respondents mistakenly enter the date as DDMMYY rather than MMYYYY which causes months larger than 12. Our approach is to code them as implausible values as we don't know whether perhaps the respondent entered MMDDYY.

Some years might be implausible but we leave them like that anyways for the user to decide what to do with it. In more recent countries, the plausible range has been reduced to 1900+ to force the respondent to enter something plausible.

In newly collected datasets e.g. Croatia, the data collection was adjusted resulting in separate month and year variables so this process does not have to be carried out. However, the variable names in the national data may not match the names in the EDF therefore it is important to ensure that the date variable names are the same in both datasets and they are appropriately labelled.

2.5 PART 5: Special answer categories and missing values

Special answers and missing values in the raw data are represented by specific numeric codes (e.g., 9, 99, 99999). These numeric codes vary between countries and require individual identification for each dataset. To identify which numeric code corresponds to which code in Blaise, the current approach is to manually cross-reference the data with the core. However, this process needs improvement. One potential solution is to import the data into SPSS and explore automated methods for identification.

The way we code the special answer categories differs for continuous and categorical variables. For continuous variables, the special answers and missing values are coded as missing values to maintain the continuity of the variable which is conducted in "5_SpecialAnswers". The following conversions are applied:

Value in data (example)	Missing code	Label	Code in Blax
9999	.a	Don't know	DK
9998	.b	Refusal	RF
9993	.c	Not applicable	NA
9991	.d	Never	Never

Value in data (example)	Missing code	Label	Code in Blax
9988	.e	Mainly work from home	WrkHome
9985	.f	Not at all	Notall
9985	.g	Not working or homemaker	Home

For categorical variables, the special answers are manually recoded as additional answer categories. To identify the corresponding recoded values, please check the *label list*. For instance:

Value in data (example) and recoded value	Label	Code in Blax
recode fer11_* (89 = 8)	None of the above	Nota
recode fer12_* (89 = 14)	Nobody	Nobody
recode wel03_* (89 = 20)	Nota	Nota
recode inc08_* (89 = 12)	Nobody	Nobody

One challenge that might arise is when country-specific values have not been appropriately coded, resulting in values that are already assigned as special values in the EDF. Another issue to consider is that some countries use special answer categories as country-specific values. These response options should not be coded as letters, as it may not be immediately clear that the value represents a country-specific category.

2.6 PART 6: Country-specific variables

Countries can adjust the core questionnaire. These deviations are marked in the Blax file using country-specific codes. The codes consist of the 3 digit country code and 1 digit for the different questions (e.g., 2001, 2002). For handling country-specific questions and response options, it's best to use a separate do-file that labels the country-specific variables. This approach facilitates updating the data and maintaining the labelling for country-specific variables consistently.

Some variables are by definition country-specific. The following response labels are always country-specific and need to be coded based on the overview provided by the national team:

- Region variables
- Education variables
- Language variables
- Wealth range variables
- Income range variables
- Payment range variables
- Religion variables (sometimes)

To ensure that country-specific values are preserved when merging data from different countries, it is essential to code the response categories with country-specific values.

When dealing with country-specific variables, these variables already have a country code and do not require adding a country code to the response option. Thus, the response options are coded as 1, 2, 3, etc. In turn, if a non-country specific variable has a country-specific response option, it is necessary to code it using the country code. Ensure that the response values for country-specific questions start with a unique identifier "01" followed by the specific value (e.g., 3901 instead of 3918).

One variable that requires attention is education. The EDF contains education variables both with and without the suffix "ISCED." The version without the ISCED suffix contains country-specific education levels provided by the national team, while the one with the ISCED suffix contains standardized levels. The national team will provide guidance on how to recode country-specific education levels into the ISCED categories. If a country lacks country-specific education levels (dem07), the variable should be kept to avoid confusing users who look for that variable, and it can be coded as a country-specific response.

When dealing with variables that have multiple response options (SETOF) and include country-specific response options, be cautious not to code them as country-specific. Blaise automatically generates additional variables for such cases, so the country-specific options should be appropriately identified and treated in the do-file to ensure accurate data representation. Additionally, ensure that the syntax contains no recode or replace commands so that the same do-file can be used for updates.

Optional and 'old' questions

The core questionnaire includes a few optional items, and countries have the flexibility to decide whether to retain them or modify certain scales. Specifically, the items FER25, FER26, and FER27 can be either completely deleted or shortened by removing items FER25g, FER25h, and FER26 (items c, d, g, and i). Additionally, the item INC04 is optional and serves as a valuable multi-item question to capture social exclusion. However, to reduce the length of the questionnaire, countries may choose to omit it. As they are still a part of the core questionnaire, these questions are not considered country-specific. Miller items (FER30) are also optional and will be coded as country-specific. Countries have the option to include Miller items, Theory of Planned Behaviour items, or none of them based on their preferences and research needs.

Furthermore, some questions have been excluded from the core questionnaire to reduce its length. As a result, some countries may have included them while newer countries did not. In the past, we coded these questions as country-specific, but these questions are no longer considered country specific as they were a part of a previous version of the core questionnaire.

The EDF contains all questions that have ever been fielded. If a country did not include a specific question, it will be empty. The decision on whether to drop the variable (resulting in different variables across datasets) or to add a new missing value (e.g., ".x not fielded in country") needs to be carefully considered and discussed.

2.7 PART 7: Break-off

A break-off refers to when a respondent quits the survey before reaching the final question. Those cases are marked with the missing value “.h incomplete survey”. Respondents who quit the survey in the first two sections, DEM or LHI, are removed from the dataset.

It is important that the variables are in the correct order as if they are not the break offs will not be recorded in the correct section of the survey. For instance, in Norway and Croatia the country specific variables for dem15_cntcode (social media use), wrk16a_cntcode (likelihood of finding a job in 12 months) and wrk42_cntcode (likelihood of partner finding a job in 12 months) were named incorrectly and were ordered at the end of the survey as opposed to in their respective sections (i.e. DEM and WRK), causing errors in the break-offs.

Variables that have a filter such as the frequency variables that are repeated have point missing values to account for the respondents who did not have to answer these questions. However, there are some variables that have no filter and should therefore not have any point missing as it is mandatory to provide an answer to these questions. Point missing values in these questions still occur because some values are pre-filled in the dataset (e.g. wrk08) and therefore, the code does not detect break-offs correctly. For example, if a respondent dropped off in the earlier sections such as DEM or LHI, any answers that are prefilled for variables later in the survey already have a response. In particular, the GEN section has many variables with prefilled values (gen09 gen13 gen16 gen17 gen23 gen27 gen30 gen31).

Another problem with the code is that it assigns a .h for SETOF variables. For example, if inc03_2 was answered then the break-off is assigned to inc03_3 even though it would be in the next variable.

2.8 PART 8: Checks and clean-up

After completing all data processing steps, it is crucial to perform a thorough check of the final dataset before proceeding with data documentation. The following key aspects need to be carefully examined:

1. Ensure there are no duplicate respondent IDs (respid), as each respondent should have a unique identifier.
2. Verify the format of respid, which typically consists of country letters followed by a numeric value (e.g., XX000000). The respid format should conform to this standard.
3. Review the age range to ensure that all respondents fall within the appropriate age group. Any out-of-range cases need to be discussed.
4. Check the variable labels, response labels, and missing values to make sure they are all labelled.
5. Drop any variables that were generated during data processing but are no longer needed.

3 FAQ

Destring and non-numeric characters

Sometimes, the DESTRING command might fail to work due to blanks in variables that should be numeric but are stored as string variables, particularly in date variables.

To address this issue, execute the following command:

```
quietly findname, type(string) local(String) foreach v of local String { list `v'
if regexm(`v', " ") & !regexm(`v', "[A-Z]") & regexm(`v', "[0-9]") }
```

Alternatively, this code can also detect non-numeric characters in variables:

```
foreach n of varlist [VARIABLES] { capture drop non_numeric generate byte
non_numeric = indexnot(`n', "0123456789.-/") tab `n' if non_numeric }
```

Uniquely identified respid and ISCO code

If the number of **respid** increases after merging the ISCO codes, ensure that ISCO codes uniquely identify occupation; otherwise, observations might be duplicated to match each number.

Different missing value codes in different languages

Special answers may still appear even though the code runs. In countries with two languages, the same special answer might receive different codes. Check whether the value only appears in one language but not the other.

Merging with EDF

Country codes are stored in EDF. If the raw data does not merge with EDF:

- If the APPEND command does not work, adjust format variables and try again.
- Sometimes, the following error code occurs if the format in the raw data differs from the format in EDF: "Error code: variable is float in master but str in using data."
- Execute `destring [VARIABLE], replace.`
- A variable might not have been linked with the EDF because it is written differently than in the EDF (e.g., all lowercase letters, a combination of numbers and underscores, zeros in numbers). This is especially the case in early versions of the data.
- Additionally, the variable might be stored as numeric in the EDF but as a string in the data (e.g., due to non-numeric values).

4 Resources

For further information on coding, refer to the DIME Data Handbook available at:
<https://worldbank.github.io/dime-data-handbook/coding.html>.